

Performance of reduced graphene oxide (RGO) as active material for electrochemical supercapacitor applications

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Abstract

Beyond pristine graphene, reduced graphene oxide with a few layers also find important applications in many areas including electrochemical devices. In this context, the reduction of electrically insulating graphite oxide (GO) to reduced graphene oxide (RGO) is important. GO has wide range of oxygen functionalities; the reduction of GO significantly removes these oxygen functional groups. In the present work GO is prepared by modified hummers method and it is reduced using hydrazine [1]. The chemical and structural properties were analyzed by TGA, XRD, SEM and Raman spectroscopy. The structural changes occurred during the transition from GO to RGO is reflected in the Raman spectra. The electrochemical performance of samples were studied using cyclic voltammetry (CV) and galvanostatic charge – discharge (CD) techniques. CD measurements RGO yields a specific capacitance of 232 F/g at 0.5 A/g.

Keywords: Reduced graphene oxide,
modified Hummers method, Specific capacitance

References

1. Sungjin Park, Jinho An, Carbon, 2011, 19, 3019-3023.